

Proposed Marketing Strategy for Increasing Batik Danar Hadi Purchase Intention among Gen Y and Z

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ABSTRACT: Batik is Indonesian heritage that remains popular and have special place in Indonesia's fashion industry. Indonesian people nowadays especially generation Y and Z use batik only on certain occasions because most of them still have the impression that batik is old-fashioned and only can be used in certain events. Batik Danar Hadi is one of pioneers for batik brand in Indonesia, their products can be worn daily which not only used for formal or important occasions. This study aims to examines how ad informativeness, ad persuasiveness, and brand awareness variables will influence purchase intention on Batik Danar Hadi with generation Y and Z as the objects. After analysing the result, Researcher proposed marketing strategy to Batik Danar Hadi according to the research results. Researchers have distributed questionnaires to assess the variables of ad informativeness, ad persuasiveness, brand awareness and purchase intentions. The results of the survey were 426 respondents, 350 respondents filled in completely, 25 respondents were dropped due to invalid data (including inverse, standard deviation, and outliers), leaving 325 respondents who met the criteria. Before distributing the research questionnaires, the researcher had carried out a small sample measurement of 30 people to get suggestions, input, and comments from respondents if there were statements that could not be understood. In this study, instrument testing was carried out with reliability and validity tests, model testing, and hypothesis testing using the SmartPLS3 test tool. The researcher developed the solutions as a solution for the business issue in a form of marketing strategy. The results of this study indicate that ad informativeness and ad persuasiveness have a positive and significant effect on brand awareness, while brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

KEYWORDS: Ad Informativeness, Ad Persuasiveness, Advertising, Brand Awareness, Purchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

The fashion industry, especially the clothing business, can be said to be timeless because it has become a necessity for various groups. Although the clothing business is quite promising, diving into the fashion industry is not necessarily easy, especially selling batik products. The development of batik was initially concentrated on Solo and Yogyakarta, behind the walls of the Kingdom palace (Keraton). Even today, batik remains popular, especially in Indonesia's fashion industry. But Indonesian people nowadays use batik only on certain occasions, in daily lives they prefer using modern-oriented fashion. Public awareness to preserve culture hasn't applied in the mind yet, but it is necessary to take real actions such as normalizing the use of batik in everyday life. Batik is still under the impression that people think batik is old-fashioned and only used in official events. The clothes produced by Batik Danar Hadi are quite fashionable when compared to other batik brands because they often collaborate with well-known designers in Indonesia. So that the products from Batik Danar Hadi can be worn daily, not only for formal/important invitations as well as not only for office attire once a week. The use of batik in daily life may come naturally to senior individuals or people who are already working, but young people are often unaware of this and tend to use batik for special occasions. With the problem, Danar Hadi Batik will benefit more if they can raise the awareness of young people to use batik. The idea of this research emerged against the background of the importance of a company to have good brand awareness. The author intends to discuss Batik Danar Hadi as a fashion company which is still searching for their sustainable business strategy especially in marketing to sustain in the fashion industry and achieve a competitive advantage. The topic we want to focus on is to raise the use of batik awareness among Generation Y and Z. If public awareness about batik begins to rise, this will affect the sales of many batik companies in a positive way, especially for Batik Danar Hadi. The author has limited the research to analyze variables such as how ad informativeness (INF) and ad persuasiveness (PER) affect brand awareness (BA) and consumer purchase intentions (PI) towards Batik Danar Hadi's business. The focus of this research is on young people, especially generations Y and Z, because they have a low level of awareness and interest in using batik compared to previous generations. For this study, samples were taken from male and female customers who had never purchased products from

Batik Danar Hadi. This research uses a quantitative method by using a questionnaire as a survey tool. By knowing what factors can affect the customer's purchase intention of the batik business, Danar Hadi Batik is able to develop their marketing strategies to meet the needs and desires of consumers in the forms of a consumer's purchase intention.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ad Systematic Cues: Ad Informativeness and Ad Persuasiveness

Features of ad content design such as informativeness, persuasiveness, emotion, and interactivity can help marketers in delivering customers brand values and product information, and allowing customers to make choices based on their systematic thinking. When someone is highly driven, competent and capable, and has abundant cognitive resources in accordance with the sufficiency principle, they are more likely to choose a systematic method [1]. When making judgments, people should take into account all relevant information that has been supplied, according to the theory of systematic information processing [2]. During the purchasing process, customers might receive and analyse both persuasive and informative aspects [3]. Both the perception perspective and the content feature perspective can be used to define informativeness and persuasiveness. From the standpoint of user perception, persuasiveness refers to the customer's impression and sense of the strength of persuasiveness based on the content, whereas informativeness denotes consumer recognition and knowledge regarding information quality of the material [4, 5, 6]. While informativeness refers to a message that informs consumers about the product or service, including specific brand, price, discount, link, and physical location, persuasiveness refers to a message that transmits preferences such as emotion, net slang, humor, small conversation, or engagement [7, 8]. In the context of social media, consumers must gather all relevant information about a product or service, such as pricing, functionality, and raw materials, in order to evaluate the ad content. Informative advertisements can direct consumers toward conversion and encourage word-of-mouth marketing. The usage of persuasive components (such as Internet slang) can increase brand awareness by giving consumers a sense of innovation [9]. The ability of an advertisement to persuade viewers depends on its ability to convey emotion, comedy, or interactive features. [7, 8]. High-quality messages in advertisements tend to increase consumers' hedonic motivation, which can increase brand awareness [10]. Customers may make rational and logical comparisons between various brands and products from informative commercials, which give them enough information about the product or service [11]. Consumers may be able to better understand the value offered by the advertisements and develop an impression of the brand through the consideration process. The greater source credibility that persuasive advertisements typically have can eventually lead to higher brand awareness [12]. The inclusion of persuasive elements, such as Internet slang, can increase brand awareness by making consumers feel inventive [9].

H1 : Ad informativeness positively affects brand awareness.

H2 : Ad persuasiveness positively affects brand awareness.

Brand awareness

Brand awareness refers to the level at which consumers are familiar with a brand's name [13]. The quantification of customer brand knowledge levels and trends is implied by brand awareness [14]. Additionally, brand awareness refers to consumers' ability to recognize and remember a certain brand, which can reveal how they feel about it [15]. Brand awareness includes brand recognition and brand recall, or the degree of brand identification and recall [16]. Social media is a platform for a brand to display its service and value proposition in order to attract customers. Social media is helpful at raising customer brand identification [17]. Social media usage is one of the options for branding. But product reviews by other customers with previous experience can have an impact on brand awareness [18]. Social media has evolved into a platform for brands to disseminate their product offerings, including new product introductions, and to build brand awareness that will affect consumer reactions [19]. However, not all customers respond favourably. Results from earlier studies supported the mediation effect of brand awareness and showed a significant influence on purchase intentions [2, 20, 21, 22]. The customer's decision-making process is influenced by brand awareness and is guided by it when making a purchase [23]. Due to the fact that many brands are seriously evaluated when making a purchase, brand awareness enhances the likelihood that a brand will be considered by the customer. In this formulation brand awareness, brand trust, and client buy intents can all be enhanced by a company with a strong reputation and high brand awareness [16]. In order to acquire high purchase intention it is preferable for a business to establish brand credibility and awareness [24].

H3 : Consumer brand awareness positively affects their purchase intention.

Purchase Intention

Purchase intention measures how likely and willing people are to purchase specific goods or services [25]. We can know that in this study consumer decision making is an important key that influences purchase intention [26]. The dimension of purchase is goods that have been certified, which will later foster confidence that the goods and services are guaranteed [27]. After that, trustworthy is a condition where a person tends to trust the products or services provided. The third and final dimension, namely price sensitivity and consumer income, we know that this will greatly affect consumers' purchase intentions. Purchase intention can be a possibility that customers will buy a certain product [28]. Greater willingness to buy a product increases the likelihood of doing so, but does not guarantee that you will. On the other hand, having less willpower does not make it impossible at all to purchase. The term "purchase intention" refers to a person's behavioural tendency toward a specific product [29]. Purchase intentions are usually determined by consumers' perceived benefits and value [30].

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Sample

Researchers have distributed questionnaires to assess the variables Ad Informativeness, Ad Persuasiveness, Brand Awareness, and Purchase Intentions. The final results of the survey were 426 respondents, 350 respondents filled in completely, 25 respondents were dropped due to invalid data (including inverse, standard deviation, and outliers), leaving 325 respondents who met the criteria. Before distributing the questionnaires, the researcher had carried out face validity to obtain suggestions, input, and comments from selected respondents if there were statements that could not be understood. In this study, instrument testing was carried out with reliability and validity tests, model testing, and hypothesis testing using the SmartPLS3 test tool. The following Table I are details of the respondent's data from this study:

Table I. Respondent profile

Characteristics	Category	Percentage
Gender	Male	39.22%
	Female	60.78%
Age	15 - 25 years old	85.15%
	26 - 41 years old	13.73%
	42 - 57 years old	1.12%
Last Education Level	Senior High School	15.13%
	Diploma Degree	7.56%
	Bachelor Degree	72.83%
	Magister Degree	4.48%
Income	< Rp 2.500.000	37.82%
	Rp 2.500.000 - Rp 5.000.000	28.57%
	Rp 5.000.001 - Rp 7.500.000	15.13%
	Rp 7.500.001 - Rp 10.000.000	9.24%
	> Rp 10.000.000	9.24%
Monthly Spending	≤ Rp 700.000	16.53%
	Rp 700.000 - Rp 1.000.000	15.13%
	Rp 1.000.001 - Rp 1.500.000	14.29%
	Rp 1.500.001 - Rp 2.000.000	17.37%
	Rp 2.000.001 - Rp 3.000.000	16.53%
Domicile	≥ Rp 3.000.000	20.17%
	Central Java	64.99%
	West Java	6.16%
	Special Capital District of Jakarta	15.41%
	Other Provinces	13.45%

Source: processed primary data, 2022

Measurement scale

This research has a total of 18 questions that are used to measure ad informativeness, ad persuasiveness, brand awareness, and purchase intention variables. Each of these questions was measured using a Likert scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) [31]. Ad informativeness was measured using 5 question items by [32]. Ad persuasiveness was measured using 4 question items [33]. Brand awareness is measured using 4 question items [34]. Purchase intention is measured using 5 question items [35].

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research uses Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS 3.3.2. PLS to test the hypothesis. There are two stages in making PLS-SEM analysis, namely evaluating the measurement model through construct validity & reliability tests, also evaluating the structural model to test the direct and indirect effects of the developed model. The following is the result of data processing using PLS-SEM.

Measurement Model

To evaluate the measurement model, each construct is tested for validity and reliability. To verify the structure, convergence analysis and discriminatory validity were carried out. If the loading factor of the structure is greater than 0.5, then the structure is considered convergent [36]. In addition, it is recommended that the average variance extracted is greater than 0.5 [37]. Table 2 shows that the load factor and AVE scores of all constructs meet the recommended criteria to show convergence validity. At the same time, discriminant validity was evaluated according to the Fornell and Larcker criteria. If the square root value of each AVE structure is greater than its correlation with other potential structures, then the structure is considered to have passed the discriminant validity test. Based on Table 3, all constructs have discriminative validity, because the AVE square root value of each construction is greater than the correlation with other potential constructs. Instrument reliability test using Cronbach Alpha and composite reliability if the value is greater than 0.70 then the instrument is considered reliable.

Table II. Construct reliability and validity results

Construct	Item	Outer Loading	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Ad Informativeness	INF1	0.799	0.846	0.889	0.616
	INF2	0.755			
	INF3	0.796			
	INF4	0.742			
	INF5	0.828			
Ad Persuasiveness	PER1	0.704	0.73	0.832	0.554
	PER2	0.794			
	PER3	0.718			
	PER 4	0.757			
Brand Awareness	BA1	0.782	0.824	0.876	0.586
	BA2	0.713			
	BA3	0.768			
	BA4	0.74			
	BA5	0.822			
Purchase Intention	PI1	0.737	0.822	0.883	0.654
	PI2	0.787			
	PI3	0.867			
	PI4	0.838			

Source: processed primary data, 2022

From the results of SmartPLS data processing in the outer loading section, it can be seen from the results of the large sample validity test in the table above. The minimum requirement for outer loading in SmartPLS is 0.7. Indicators that have a value between 0.40 and less than 0.70 are not removed if they do not affect AVE and CR. In the table above all question items have met the minimum requirements or can be said to be valid [36]. The table above also shows the results of the large sample reliability test from SmartPLS. It can be concluded from the table that all the variables used in this study are stated to have reliable instruments because they have a Cronbach's Alpha value of more than 0.6.

Table III. Discriminant validity results

	Ad Informativeness	Ad Persuasiveness	Brand Awareness	Purchase Intention
Ad Informativeness	0.785			
Ad Persuasiveness	0.551	0.744		
Brand Awareness	0.323	0.367	0.766	
Purchase Intention	0.354	0.535	0.415	0.809

Source: processed primary data, 2022

Measurement Model Structural Model Assessment

After evaluating the measurement model, structural model analysis was carried out to test the proposed hypothesis. This analysis was carried out by testing the hypotheses of direct and indirect effects. The following Figure 1 is the results of research using PLS-SEM analysis.

Figure 1. Path Coefficient Value dan P-Value

To find out the relationship and significance of one variable to another, a hypothesis test was carried out. The hypothesis test in this study uses the T-statistics value and the original sample on the path coefficient to see the relationship between variables and the significance of the relationship. In the direct effect test, the analysis of the structural model contained in table IV shows that ad informativeness has a positive and significant effect on brand awareness ($\beta = 0.174$, p-value < 0.01). The results of the analysis also show that ad persuasiveness has a positive and significant effect on brand awareness ($\beta = 0.271$, p-value < 0.01). The test results prove that brand awareness has a significant positive effect on purchase intention ($\beta = 0.415$, p-value < 0.01).

Table IV. Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Description
H1 (INF → BA)	0.174	0.063	2.75	0.006	Significant
H2 (PER → BA)	0.271	0.06	4.488	0.000	Significant
H3 (BA → PI)	0.415	0.047	8.89	0.000	Significant

Source: processed primary data, 2022

In the direct effect test, the analysis of the structural model contained in table IV shows that ad informativeness has a positive and significant effect on brand awareness ($\beta = 0.174$, p-value <0.01). The results of the analysis also show that ad persuasiveness has a positive and significant effect on brand awareness ($\beta = 0.271$, p-value <0.01). The test results prove that brand awareness has a significant positive effect on purchase intention ($\beta = 0.415$, p-value <0.01).

Discussion

Ad persuasiveness directly affects brand awareness, with a statistical significance of 0.000 [33]. Based on this research, the persuasiveness of ad content supports the effectiveness of advertising from their creative advertisement. The ad persuasiveness can determine the effectiveness of advertisement faster than the numbers of sales generated. Therefore, investment in increasing content from ad persuasiveness will be beneficial to increase brand awareness, so that the second hypothesis can be accepted. Brand awareness has a positive and significant relationship to purchase intention, this makes the third hypothesis accepted. This statement has been supported by several previous studies which explains that according to academic studies, brand awareness is the key barrier to any brand-related search and has a direct impact on consumers' purchase decisions [38]. Departing from this, we can see that the greater level of consumer awareness about a brand, the greater purchase intention they have. From the analysis and relate it with the literature review and the preliminary research, we can know that influencers who have a reliable public image may increase the perceived credibility of the advertisement [39]. This findings shows that to boost the content so that young people could be more aware about a product is by make an advertisement using influencers. A social media influencer is a content creator that has a specific amount of followers on social media and has expertise in an area. Consumer attitudes regarding a brand may be influenced by the influencer, who also has unlimited commercial potential. When customers are an influencer's followers, their affection for the influencer may inspire them to learn more about the influencer's way of life and expertise. Influencers can establish a para-social contact with followers by sharing their experience [40, 41]. Additionally, previous research indicates that influencers' social media advertisements increase customer connection with a brand more than business posers. Additionally, consumers leave more supportive comments under influencer ads than business ads [11].

V. CONCLUSION

To raise brand awareness for Batik Danar Hadi, particularly among members of generations Y and Z, the researcher came up with a few research questions. The researcher used questionnaires to determine what Batik Danar Hadi's potential customers thought about the social media content that caught their attention. Based on the findings, Batik Danar Hadi should implement some strategy to raise potential customer's brand awareness. This research has test results assisted by SmartPLS3 which will later produce several conclusions, so that it can make it easier for readers to understand the research results. The first finding, namely ad informativeness, in this study proved to influence brand awareness. This means that quite informative content from a brand will affect their knowledge of a brand and affect their brand awareness. It goes the same with the second hypothesis that ad persuasiveness in this study proved to have a positive and significant effect on brand awareness. This means that interactive and interesting messages from an advertisement can form consumer stimuli and will have a positive impact on brand awareness. The last finding is brand awareness has a positive effect on purchase intention. This implies that consumers feel more inclined to make purchases when they are more aware of a brand. Researchers offer suggestions for execution in the form of marketing strategies based on the research findings. Collaboration with third parties, such as young influencers and brands that appeal to young people today, is the focus. The researcher also recommended Batik Danar Hadi to focus on digital marketing for the young age segment, for more specific is Gen Y and Z.

The researcher makes an implementation plan that Batik Danar Hadi may be willing to consider implementing at the end of the section.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

We know from the last section that businesses need investment to improve how informative and convincing their advertisements are. In order to achieve these goals, innovation must be employed to boost brand recall and brand recognition among potential customers for Batik Danar Hadi. Managers have to do lots of research to get prospective brand awareness techniques so they can create powerful brand strategies that will influence consumers' purchase intentions. It might begin by concentrating on digital marketing for the younger age group, specifically Gen Y and Z. This study has several limitations, such as the age of the respondents who are predominantly 15-25 years old, which is the Z generation, which is 85.15%, while the Y generation, with an age range of 26-41 years, has a percentage of only around 13.73%. So that it can be said that there is an unequal age distribution for the respondents of this study. Next, namely the demographics of respondents centered on Central Java as much as 64.99% of the total respondents. Based on the research limitations that have been described, suggestions for further research are expected to be able to complement the limitations that exist in this study. Further research can be carried out more intensively so that the population obtained can be more diverse to increase the representativeness of the results, considering that Batik Danar Hadi are spread across various cities in Indonesia and have a target segmentation for all age groups. The last suggestion is that further research can add other variables, for example from ad heuristic cues such as influencer marketing, web advertising, and online customer reviews.

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Cite this Article: Ayu Nadia Haniah, Prawira Fajarindra Belgiawan (2023). Proposed Marketing Strategy for Increasing Batik Danar Hadi Purchase Intention among Gen Y and Z. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(1), 229-237